

Solid fuels in oxy-fuel applications

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coal

Source: <http://www.hanshennig.de/>

Helmstedterrevier.de

biomass

waste / refuse derived fuels

Wienchol et al., "Waste-to-energy technology integrated with carbon capture – Challenges and opportunities," *Energy*, 2020

Prof. R. Kneer
Spokesman of Oxyflame
Chair of German Flame / DVV

12 years

294 journal publications

45 phd theses

DVV support by stipends, joint conference activities

Pulverized fuel boiler

Plant dimensions
10-100 m

Turbulence mm - cm

Particles 10^{-4} - 10^{-5} m

Chemistry 10^{-8} m

Coal d_p 10-200 μm
 Biomass d_p < 500 μm
 Waste incineration
 $d_p \sim \text{cm}$

Flash-Pyrolysis

- heated walls 1000-1500K
- heated gas
 - N_2 , CO_2 , H_2O ,
- Particles $\sim 100 \mu m$ (coal, biomass)

Zelkowski: standardized ignition test rig

Comparison between N₂ and CO₂: ignition slower in CO₂

- Atmospheric conditions deviating from conventional firing
- Heat transfer changes
- Oxyfuel: additional reactive flue gas components!

- Reaction rate may increase while (local) energy release decreases
- → retrofitting existing plants may need a burner and oxidizer flow re-design

Torrefied poplar, 0.15 kg/h, 100-250 μm
 2.5 $\text{m}_\text{N}/\text{h}$
 $t = 0.5 \text{ s}$

C. Yildiz et al., "Pollutant Formation under Nitrogen and Carbon Dioxide Atmosphere of Torrefied Poplar in an Entrained Flow Reactor," *Energy and Fuels*, vol. 38, no. 9, pp. 8157–8167, 2024

CO₂, H₂O tri-atomic

Thermal radiation changes

Quelle: Stanger, The 4th Oxy-fuel Capacity Building Course

Pulverized fuel swirl flames

$$\frac{dI_{\lambda}^{\Omega}}{ds} = - \underbrace{(\kappa_{g,\lambda} + \kappa_{p,\lambda}) I_{\lambda}^{\Omega}}_{\text{Absorption}} - \underbrace{\sigma_{p,\lambda} I_{\lambda}^{\Omega}}_{\text{Outscattering}} + \underbrace{\frac{\sigma_{p,\lambda}}{4\pi} \int_{4\pi} I_{\lambda}^{\Omega'} \Phi_{p,\lambda}^{\Omega'} d\Omega'}_{\text{Inscattering}} + \underbrace{\epsilon_{g,\lambda} I_{b,\lambda}(T_g) + \epsilon_{p,\lambda} I_{b,\lambda}(T_p)}_{\text{Emission}}$$

- Weighted Sum of Gray Gases Model
- Full Spektrum Correlated k Model

- Particle absorption/emission
- scattering

[1] H. Schneider et al., *Fuel*, vol. 362, no. October 2023, p. 130771, 2024

[2] T. Gronarz et al., *Fuel Processing Technology*, vol. 157, pp. 76–89, Mar. 2017

[3] T. Li et al., *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 136, no. July 2020, 2021

- Location: Lausitz (Chemical park with conv. Lignite-fired power plant)
- Construction May 2006
- Participation of numerous companies (Vattenfall, Doosan, Linde, Alstom)
- First Flame mid 2008
- 30 MW_{th} (Dust firing)
- Results:
 - OF (Firing) works, changes in burner settings (swirl) necessary
 - >90% CO₂ capture, ca. 3000 t CO₂ captured

Air Firing

Oxy Firing

COAL CARBON CAPTURE AND STORAGE SITE AT SCHWARZE PUMPE, GERMANY

Forward-acting
reciprocating grate

reverse-acting grate

Roller grate

Contours of Static Temperature (k)

Aug 28, 2013
ANSYS Fluent 14.5 (3d, pbns, spe, sstk)

Example for gasification

1D model, bed conditions

$d_p = 1$ cm, $T = 1200$ K

Oxygen depletion

$C + CO_2 \rightarrow 2CO$ relevant

$C + H_2O \rightarrow CO + H_2$ less important

B. Brosch, phd thesis, RUB, 2012

TGA measurements

P. Wienchol et al., "Thermogravimetric and kinetic study of thermal degradation of various types of municipal solid waste (MSW) under N₂, CO₂ and oxy-fuel conditions," *Energy*, vol. 248, p. 123573, Jun. 2022

Impact of CO₂ clearly visible
 → flue gas recirculation

Pollutants

M. Becidan et al., "Oxyfuel Combustion of a Model MSW—An Experimental Study," *Energies*, vol. 14, no. 17, p. 5297, Aug. 2021

Characterization of the combustion behaviour of Solid Recovered Fuel under oxyfuel conditions (WOxy-fuel) IGF-grant Nr. 01/F23237N

Motivation

- Major CO₂ reduction by burning fuel in O₂-rich, **N₂-free** atmosphere
- Flue gas → ideally pure CO₂ → simplified CCS / CCU
- Resource saving & energy efficient solution for **grate firing systems?**

Role of Solid Recovered Fuel (SBS 1®)

- Low cost → made of sorted & treated nonhazardous waste streams → further reduction of CO₂ emissions
- Municipal solid waste, construction & industrial debris
- Energy recovery → direct incineration (generation of heat & electricity) or gasification (syngas)

Fixed bed reactor KLEAA

Experimental

SBS1® mean elemental content

Parameter	Value
H ₂ O	24,9 [wt. %] (o. s.)
Ash	8,3 [wt. %] (o. s.)
Volatile matter	56,8 [wt. %] (o. s.)
LHV	14,0 [MJ/kg] (o. s.)
C (TOC)	36,8 [wt. %] (o. s.)
C (TIC)	0,18 [wt. %] (o. s.)
Biogenic C	64,0 [% of total carbon]
H	5,3 [wt. %] (o. s.)
O	22,6 [wt. %] (o. s.)
N	1,4 [wt. %] (o. s.)
S	0,17 [wt. %] (o. s.)
Cl	0,39 [wt. %] (o. s.)
d ₅₀	17 [mm]
d ₉₅	35 [mm]

o. s. = original substance

Oxyfuel gas mixture	O ₂ [vol.-%]	CO ₂ [vol.-%]
Oxy 20/80	20	80
Oxy 30/70	30	70
Oxy 40/60	40	60
Air	21	-

Parameter	Value
Fuel	SBS1®
Primary oxidizer	5 [m ³ /h] (constant)
Secondary oxidizer	12,5 [m ³ /h] (constant)
T°C combustion chamber	~ 900 [°C]
Primary air	5 [m ³ /h] (constant)
Secondary air	12,5 [m ³ /h] (constant)

Outlook

- Higher O₂-concentration → exponential growth of combustion parameters, faster flame propagation & greater heat release, significant NO_x-reduction
- O₂/CO₂ ratio of 30/70 vol.% → optimal combustion & quasi-stationary duration
- Transfer → - pilot waste incinerator ROFEA at IED in Stuttgart

Team

Institute for Technical Chemistry (ITC),
Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)

Institute for Energy Process Engineering and Dynamics in
Energy Systems – IED, University of Stuttgart

REMONDIS GmbH & Co. KG,
Erfstadt

Standart kiln line for clinker production

1st and 2nd generation oxyfuel kiln line for clinker production

Buzzi Unicem SpA - Dyckerhoff GmbH,
SCHWENK Zement GmbH & Co. KG

Vicat S.A.

HeidelbergCement AG

Mergelstetten, Germany

NO flue gas recirculation

Fully operational 2028

IGF 24003 N: Cement Production with RDF in Oxyfuel Atmosphere

Refuse Derived Fuel

> 70 %

Modelling combustion behaviour in CO₂

Forecast of operational performance

- Solid fuel combustion without N_2 changes:
 - Volatile chemistry
 - Char conversion
 - Radiation
- Flue gas recirculation increases gas volume and CO_2 (+ H_2O) concentration
- Concepts exist for pulverized fuels, waste and cement
 - Cement with largest steps forward
 - Full industrial roll out expected for 2029/2030